

Birth year	Names	First paper	PhD ступінь	Retired	Sex	Characteristics	Life years
1995	Merve Gürel	2014			w	Turkish Instructor of Department of Modern Languages	
1995	Nitika Rani	2016	No		w	Indian assistant of Department music	
1995	Liviu Popa	2017	No			Belgian Master's student of Social and Cultural Anthropology	
1995	Thomas Nicholson	2018	No			Canadian composer, keyboardist and violinist	